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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable brings together the key content for the MIRRI business plan and contains the text of the 3rd Iteration Business Case prepared and printed in early 2015. The Financial Plan included in the business case has been presented as *Deliverable 4.1 Financial Plan* for submission to the European Commission in April 2015. The Preparatory Phase has reached a point where the MIRRI infrastructure, governance, operations and activities are well defined. Documents needed for the negotiation of the MIRRI European Research Infrastructure Consortium (MIRRI-ERIC) are drafted including the Statutes, Partner Charter and the Rules of Operation. The cost estimates are now more robust and there is an indication of which countries are keen to establish MIRRI. Thus MIRRI is in a strong position to prepare content for its business plan and has indeed already published its 3rd Iteration Business Case to use by partners to engage potential funders of the MIRRI-ERIC. This business plan content defines the problems European Research faces and provides the MIRRI offer which will deliver solutions to enable high quality research and innovation to drive microbial science and underpin the European bioeconomy.

For more than a century microbial resources have been recognized as the essential raw material for the advancement of health, and later for biotechnology, agriculture, food technology and for research in the Life Sciences. This has led to the establishment of microbial domain resource centres (mBRC) to provide live cultures to foster and support the development of basic and applied science in various European countries. Over recent years a number of initiatives have been undertaken to coordinate access to these resources to present a better offer to Europe and these have created the opportunity for the establishment of a not-for-profit pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI, www.mirri.org). The European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) provides the ideal platform for the development of this infrastructure which takes the interoperability and accessibility of resources and data to a higher level. The current independent, often institutional policies and managed processes will be adapted by partner mBRCs to harmonize holdings, services, the training offer and accession policy and share expertise. Better managed resources coupled with improved interaction with stakeholders will lead to further discovery in all areas of the Life Sciences. Influenced and directed by user needs, the MIRRI Partners will coordinate National Nodes of unparalleled depth and breadth of microbial resources; the infrastructure will improve access to enhanced quality microorganisms in an appropriate legal framework and to resource-associated data in a more interoperable way. The MIRRI Central Coordinating Unit will function as the core of MIRRI established through a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The National Nodes and national mBRCs will retain their own legal entity but control of some elements of their operations will be transferred to the MIRRI-ERIC. These functions include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters. mBRC participation in the MIRRI National Nodes will be governed by commitments made in the Partner Charter which will include delivery of high quality data to agreed standards, participation in capacity building programmes and a commitment to deliver the MIRRI communication and outreach strategy to stakeholders particularly to bio-industry. MIRRI is putting in place an associate partner scheme to help those wishing to join MIRRI but need assistance in meeting the Partner Charter.

MISSION: The MIRRI offer to science and bioindustry

MIRRI will remove fragmentation in resource and service availability and focus on fundamental needs and challenges and thus will:

- a. facilitate legally protected and regulative compliant access to resources in mBRCs and associated data to maintain a comprehensive supply of biological material in keeping with the demands of the research community;
 - implement a common acquisition policy to increase capacity and engender trust in order to facilitate access to materials from countries of mega diversity
 - link member mBRC holdings with contextual data and publicly available data generated on these microorganisms
 - ensure that key reference strains from publications are available for the furtherance of science;
- b. provide a single access entry point to state-of-the-art microbial biological services and to expert and technical platforms to enable researchers to carry out in-house research on mBRC holdings;
- c. improve the interoperability between mBRCs and overarching, as well as complementary data offers;
- d. implement quality management including standardised procedures, best practices and appropriate tools to increase the quality of the resources collected and their associated data as well as performed services;
- e. establish relationships with other European research infrastructures and Pan-European organisations in related fields;
- f. perform research to add value to strains, match and pool services for public and private institutions and launch joint activities;
- g. provide coordinated external user access to the research infrastructure;
- h. engage the internal researcher and technologist community to implement common standards, share technologies and knowledge and coordinate to resolve operational problems and address user community needs

Added value of MIRRI

Individual mBRCs cannot present global solutions to microbiological needs; this requires a coordinated approach by a consortium of national mBRCs guided by their stakeholders. No single country currently offers a complete coverage of microbial diversity and associated services and therefore an overarching European organisation of the national distributed infrastructures is required to make best use of current capacity, bridge gaps and address the needs of biotechnology today:

- Economy of scale: **together** MIRRI can afford the full range of often expensive technologies needed to explore biodiversity; offer a more **integrated spectrum** of equipment, data, background knowledge and services
- **Together** MIRRI provides access to the entire spectrum of microorganisms accessible via a single “entry”-point
- **Together** MIRRI sets European standards of collection, curation and analysis
- **Together**, MIRRI sets ambitious, collaborative research goals over extended periods

- **Together**, MIRRI can share best practices, standards, data and personnel; can exchange personnel for sabbaticals, organize courses together, offer vocational and professional training and education

MIRRI will set the framework for mBRCs to change their operations so that they can underpin and improve the microbiological sciences more effectively and efficiently. This will include the provision of standard strain data sets that will enable users to access the microorganisms' yet unrecognised potential, deliver regulatory compliance and facilitate knowledge and technology transfer. The mBRC commitments to this are defined more fully in the Partner Charter. Thus they will have impact on the bioeconomies of Europe, providing integrated solutions to the Grand Challenges and facilitate the generation of knowledge from data. MIRRI will work with other ESFRI infrastructures providing the essential microbial strain data and expertise to facilitate the use of microorganisms in research and development.

MIRRI will work to counteract the declining basic taxonomic expertise. MIRRI provides coherence in the application of quality standards, homogeneity in data storage and management and sharing of the workload to help release the hidden potential of microorganisms. With its anticipated intense dialog with users and stakeholders, MIRRI has the potential to add value to research innovation, bring together and foster currently isolated research projects. MIRRI will integrate services and resources, bridging the gap between the organisms and envisaged biotechnological solutions and products in order to enhance competitiveness of Europe's bio-industry, including the support of SME's business.

The goal can only be achieved by a distributed research infrastructure with operational units in most, if not all, European Member States. MIRRI will be implemented under an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) which is described in its statutes. The MIRRI-ERIC will implement a work programme as adopted by the Assembly of Members and provide the common gateway to resources and expertise available in the individual mBRCs. It will operate on the basis of a central organisation, managed by the Central Coordinating Unit. The user services will be facilitated by the nodes via the collaboration of the respective national stakeholder community. The individual microbial domain biological resource centres (mBRCs) maintain their own legal status. The nodes facilitate the respective national stakeholder community, universities, bio-industries, policy makers and scientists to access microbial knowledge. MIRRI invites stakeholders to participate in its further development to meet its objectives.

DRIVING A SUCCESSFUL BIOECONOMY

The European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) establishes pan-European structures to drive innovation and provide the resources, technologies and services necessary to underpin research thus ensuring improved pathways to discovery for the future (<http://ec.europa.eu/research/esfri/>). The ESFRI strategy recognises the weakness of fragmented individual policies and supports a coherent strategy on research infrastructures in Europe, which facilitates multilateral initiatives and provides Europe with the most up-to-date Research Infrastructures (RI). Science frontiers are evolving and knowledge-based technologies need to be used more widely. MIRRI will integrate services and resources, and encourage innovative solutions providing an integrated solution to microbial resource provision (Figure 1). It will provide coherence in the application of quality standards, homogeneity in data storage and management, and workload sharing to help scientists release the full potential of microorganisms.

Innovation has been placed at the heart of the Europe 2020 strategy and is the best means of successfully tackling major global and societal challenges, which are becoming more urgent by the day. There is wide recognition within Europe and beyond that harnessing the full value in biological materials and processes provides the opportunity to create value from new products and services within a more resilient, eco-efficient bioeconomy (see, for example, ¹Geoghegan-Quinn, ²The European Commission on the bioeconomy and H2020, ³OECD bioeconomy 2030).

Microbiological diversity and well described microbial resources will play a key role in underpinning the bioeconomy and driving economic growth through successful biotechnological innovation. Harvesting the full value in such organisms is fundamental to agribusiness, industrial biotechnology health technology, biofuel production and, more fundamentally to new industrial policy and green growth. These are in turn, fundamental to the delivery of continuing European success in a world that is globalising at a startlingly unprecedented pace.

¹ Geoghegan-Quinn, M., 2010. Commissioner for Research, Innovation and Science, 'Bioeconomy for a better life'. Conference on the Knowledge-based bioeconomy towards 2020, Brussels, 14 September.

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/index_en.htm

³ <http://www.oecd.org/futures/long-termtechnologicalsocietalchallenges/thebioeconomyto2030designingapolicyagenda.htm>

Figure 1. Coordination and a holistic approach to data management at the heart of the MIRRI offer

Realizing sustained growth and harnessing a successful bioeconomy will not, however, happen spontaneously and will require private and public sectors to work together to develop specific initiatives plus a supportive environment for the bioeconomy to emerge. A well-integrated research infrastructure that underpins such efforts will be essential.

Impact of MIRRI on the bioeconomy

Current demand is mainly driven by existing holdings and services. The current MIRRI 13 Partner mBRCs distributed about 198,000 individual resources to users, requested in 109,000 individual orders in the three year period between 2010 and 2012. These were provided equally (50:50) nationally and internationally; 60% of these were shipped to users located in the non-profit sector and 40% to profit making organizations. The global figures for supply from the World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC) affiliate collections are estimated at around 0.5 million per year⁴. The number of microbiologists in both the academic and industrial environment in need of microbial resources is huge and difficult to estimate. These users can be defined as those seeking resources from mBRCs for their research and those requesting deposition of resources into mBRCs. According to wiki.answer.com the number of Universities in Europe is around 400. Adding another 600 research institutes that encompass at least one biological department the total number of European institutes involved in microbiological research would be around 1,000. For SMEs the Annual Report 2013⁵ gives total numbers but does not specify those which are working in the R&D area of microbiology. The MIRRI broader material and extended data offer will engage this larger user community; published estimates demonstrate that mBRCs provide

⁴ Smith, D. (2012). Culture Collections. *Advances in Applied Microbiology* 79, 73–118.

⁵ SME Annual Report 2013 http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/sme/facts-figures-analysis/performance-review/index_en.htm

only 1% of the microorganisms used in microbiological research therefore the potential in revealing novel insights in basic as well as applied research is enormous.

The number of resources to be deposited in public mBRCs is likewise difficult to estimate and data are presently available only from a survey performed on microbial holdings financed by the German Research Council. Based upon MIRRI designed 'key strain' criteria about 1,100 strains should be deposited annually in mBRCs to protect public investments. Based on the number of 1,000 European institutes indicated above, about 110,000 microbiological resources should be deposited annually in MIRRI partner mBRCs. Assuming that each of the 36 MIRRI partners and party mBRCs add an average 400 strains annually to their holdings only about 14,000 of the estimated 110,000 resources (about 13%) worth depositing could be made available annually to the public. In order to make available all novel microbial 'key' resources, each MIRRI member would have to add on average around 2,600 strains to their holdings annually.

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) statistics report that over 4,500 organisms were deposited as part of the publication of patents in 2012⁶. Additionally, it must be noted that microbial resource centres are not the source of all strains on which research is based. The majority of the 20,000 strains cited in 8 European journals on microbiology are not included in mBRC holdings⁷. The European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation Research Infrastructures⁸ estimates that there are around 500,000 life scientists in the research landscape. Many of whom are microbiologists reliant on high quality microbial resources. The "bioeconomy" as a whole is worth nearly €2 trillion and provides approximately 22 million jobs in Europe alone across sectors as diverse as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, food, chemicals and biofuels⁹. These few facts indicate that the market for strains of microorganisms for MIRRI partner mBRCs is potentially enormous and the potential to improve access to accelerate the rate of discovery is consequently large. However, mBRCs must be proactive in helping generate new added-value products and services and need a coordinated strategy to be cost effective and efficient. Coordination of access to microbial resources and services will pave the way for innovation in a much more efficient manner than hitherto. At a time of public budget constraints, major demographic changes and increasing global competition there remains too much fragmentation and costly duplication, as well as dangerous gaps, in the European offering. Harnessing the power of networking of collections is essential if efficiency gains are to be realised.

Resources are not currently available in the "right" sort of way – in effect they are "hidden", both at the level of knowing what resources and first order data are available (so that effort is continuously wasted "reinventing the wheel" through *de novo* isolation and description of organisms already well understood) and, perhaps more importantly, in translating that data into useable, accessible knowledge that has immediate added value.

There needs to be better interrogation of the full potential of organisms in the field and the ability of potential users to access such knowledge needs to be much more efficient and transparent, with the supply of knowledge and the demand for it being significantly more robustly matched up. In short, the enterprise driving the utilisation of microbial resources in

⁶ <http://www.wipo.int/ipstats/en/statistics/micros/index.html>

⁷ Stackebrandt, E. (2010). Diversification and focusing: strategies of microbial culture collections. *Trends in Microbiology* 18, 283–287.

⁸ Enabling Science EU support to research infrastructures in the life sciences. (2013). European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Directorate B — European Research Area, Unit B.3 — Research Infrastructure

⁹ EuropaBio (2012) The tax, finance and regulatory framework and global policy comparison. European Commission. <http://www.europabio.org/biotechnology-europe-tax-finance-and-regulatory-framework-and-global-policy-comparison>

the bioeconomy needs to become demand sensitive and forward looking and exploratory in a way that it has not been for a generation.

MIRRI will provide open access for data and materials generated with public funding establishing clear rights on access and use but where it adds value it may develop tools for which it charges. mBRCs will continue to charge for supply of strains whilst seeking innovative mutually beneficial ways to supply strains into research programmes. Some services will be market driven. MIRRI will work to increase capacity to facilitate acquisition of strains to underpin European life sciences and develop a common accession policy to protect the public investment by funders in developing these resources. MIRRI will work with its members to improve their business plans and expand their private funding. Most importantly a closer relationship will be built with researchers by opening up facilities to enable knowledge and technology transfer providing access to facilities, biological materials and know how to accelerate the discovery processes.

MIRRI enhances the role of mBRCs

For more than a century microbial resources have been recognized as essential raw material for the advancement of basic and applied research in Life Sciences. The recognition that such resources need to be maintained and made readily available for research led to the establishment of mBRCs in most European countries. However, these mBRCs tend to work in isolation, have different funding models and are prone to significant gaps and duplication. A properly networked European system that ensures the interoperability and accessibility of high quality resources and data is essential for the growth of our bioeconomy. That same system has to deliver on the vision of a knowledge-based, not just data or material-based, bioeconomy and shine a clear light on the full useable value of our microbial heritage. This is what the pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) sets out to achieve.

The role of mBRCs in microbial resource management

- Preservation and supply of biological resources
- Performance of R&D – adding value
- Conservation of biodiversity
- Repositories for protection of intellectual property
- Enabling the tracking of genetic materials
- Microbiological services such as isolation of pure cultures, optimisation of growth conditions, identification of organisms, quality control and environmental sampling

The OECD best practice guidelines for BRCs¹⁰ define the role of biological resource centres and provide operational details for mBRCs. MIRRI will provide capacity building programmes, share standard operating procedures and provide common solutions to facilitate the transition from traditional culture collection to mBRC. Importantly, through an

¹⁰ OECD (2007). Best Practice Guidelines for Biological Resource Centers (June 2007), http://www.oecd.org/document/36/0,3343,en_2649_34537_38777060_1_1_1_1,00.html

associate partner scheme, it will coordinate their development, networking and output to better protect and deliver these resources to underpin European research. Currently, Europe faces five fundamental challenges that mean the use of microbial resources in the search for microbial solutions to the grand challenges and in the bioeconomy is seriously sub-optimal and thus reduces European competitiveness:

1. FUNDAMENTAL UNCERTAINTY ABOUT THE FULL VALUE INHERENT IN MICROBIAL RESOURCES AND HOW TO ACCESS IT

The idea of releasing the “full value” in microbial resources is pivotal to delivery of the bioeconomy. Simply put, such value is the potential for use of microbial resources, as well as the biological systems and components therein, in basic and applied science as well as in innovation (for example, the potential that may be inherent in some fungal metabolites to act as new generation antimicrobials). There is a need to be able to focus the expertise and capacity of mBRCs to provide the specific resources to facilitate discovery of solutions to some of our grand challenges such as antimicrobials for control of resistant diseases and accelerate discovery in healthcare. Greater rigour and greater cooperation is required to ensure that research matches industry and societal demand. The broader user community need to be brought into a strategic discussion with MIRRI on addressing such gaps in the short, medium and longer terms.

There remains huge uncertainty about where such untapped value lies and the systems for discovery need to be made much more efficient and productive. mBRCs are both repositories of materials as well as huge amounts of data on microbial system functioning but the integration of systems data with organism taxonomy, functionality and geographical origin (amongst other factors) is at best patchy.

Furthermore, there are large gaps and overlaps in the pool of microbial resources that are described, with concomitant gaps in scientific expertise. In short, prediction and discovery around releasing the full value is currently very limited, inefficient and often is as hit and miss as the toss of a coin. To improve this situation key obstacles to research need to be tackled in a co-ordinated way, which in turn will improve the provision of microbial resources beyond what is currently supplied by individual microbial resource collections.

2. MAJOR SHORTCOMINGS IN THE WAY DATA ON MICROBIAL RESOURCES IS PRESENTED.

Addressing the gaps in microbial resources needs to be accompanied by addressing gaps in data about such resources. There currently are significant gaps, both in terms of primary data describing organisms as well as second-order knowledge on their full value (i.e. the potential functions and uses of microbial resources and associated biological systems).

New data needs to be accumulated but before this existing data needs to be used in a more focussed and intelligent way. Ensuring data on microbial strains is interoperable with other data sets allows meta-data analysis and new knowledge generation. Integration of habitat, taxonomic, genomic and phenotypic data can be interrogated smartly to reveal interesting chemistry and utilisable metabolic information in the search for chemical leads. Data accumulation aligned to the needs of potential users will ensure relevance of the microbial resources and facilitate their uptake and use to provide innovative solutions and discover active compounds. A coordinated approach across the mBRCs in the infrastructure will enable the prioritisation of filling data gaps and an obligation of member collections to ensure quality of data and to seek mechanisms to add value will increase the data offer and provide transparency to reveal new uses.

3. THE QUALITY AND REPRODUCIBILITY OF MICROBIAL SCIENCE NEED SIGNIFICANT IMPROVEMENT

It is apparent that Europe depends on strains of uncertain origin for its microbiological research output⁶. Only 194 strains of those cited in the articles of 8 European microbiology journals were sourced or were deposited in public service collections. This implies that 99% of the published literature is based on microbiology that is hard to replicate. The efficiency costs of this are huge, with much published research being difficult or impossible to replicate across laboratories and effective knowledge transfer effectively blocked.

mBRCs are the best place for storage, as the long-term maintenance and distribution of strains are their key functions. It is crucial that public sequence data bases are backed up by making the material on which the sequence was made available to examine if doubts arise about the data. Additionally, as technologies develop or different areas of the genome need to be sequenced the biological material or at least the DNA must be available. We need to ensure that science has a sound basis and that the correct organisms are used; a backup is needed to ensure biological materials are there for confirmation of results and for exploration of aberrant results ensuring good science.

4. MICROBIAL DIVERSITY SERVICES NEED TO BE TRUSTED AND SUSTAINED

Currently, poor accessibility to microbiological services and gaps in expertise linked to sub-optimal coordination across mBRCs impede the biotechnologist from getting the help needed in their work. There is a need to deepen and sustain service provision by enhancing microbial science capability and capacity whilst engendering trust in the quality and provenance of such services.

Innovative solutions need to be found to the critical questions for improved mechanisms for delivery of resources and services. The diminishing expertise in the isolation and identification of biodiversity particularly in the switch from traditional taxonomy to the molecular needs to be managed appropriately and the existing expertise coordinated and shared through a common platform. MIRRI will provide the services to access new microbial diversity to allow the biotechnologists to focus on their job to develop the products

5. THE NEED TO BE ABLE TO CAPTURE VALUE AND BENEFIT FROM MICROBIAL RESOURCES

It is essential that mechanisms for sharing benefits in terms of intellectual property rights, publications, financial rewards etc. are developed if generated from use of microorganism holdings of the partner collections, especially when taking into account the CBD-ABS Nagoya Protocol implications. MIRRI will work towards establishing best practices and keep pace with legislative decision to ensure compliance with European and national law. Additionally, by sharing technologies and enhancing data, MIRRI can help resource holders add value and discover the hidden properties in microorganisms. If this is not recognised then it cannot be released. Through characterisation MIRRI can help add value. MIRRI will work towards strategic mutually beneficial access to well described high quality organisms to drive economic growth in bio-businesses. Through such best practices MIRRI can engender trust becoming a technology standards broker and make it easier for reciprocal mutually beneficial exchange of microbial diversity.

Impact of MIRRI on resource provision

Underpinning all these challenges is the broader problem of the through-flow of skilled people, perhaps especially in the field of microbial taxonomy, where shortfalls in young talent coming through the education and training system are beginning to approach what could be a tipping point irretrievable within a generation. MIRRI proposes to answer this problem by bringing together the people we have and develop training and succession plans. The molecular taxonomy skills are in place but the phenotype taxonomy is missing in Europe. MIRRI aspires to pool data and integrate it. To add value to the data we need phenotypic taxonomists, currently only expanding elsewhere for example, China, India and Korea, to make meaningful inputs; the majority of data are outside mBRCs therefore there is a need to bring this together and add more; MIRRI needs to outreach to data producers and work with them making links to external skills in academia and using them to generate knowledge.

These are a formidable set of challenges to delivery of the benefits of a bioeconomy. No one initiative, no matter how large the investment, can hope to succeed in harvesting the full value inherent in microorganisms and microbial systems. However, Europe can do much better in terms of gathering data and turn that into useable knowledge within a developing bioeconomy. Efforts can be prioritised and coordinated to address each of the challenges set out above and, together with other existing and developing initiatives, including in the ESFRI space, much increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the bioeconomy innovation enterprise, as well as all the downstream economic and social benefits this promises, such as jobs, new business creation and a greener, cleaner and fairer economy.

The proposal presented in the remainder of this document – for the creation of a pan-European Microbial Resources Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) sets out a vision and a way forward to deliver just such improvements in efficiency and effectiveness addressing the 5 major challenges articulated here.

THE MIRRI APPROACH

The goal of MIRRI is to create a single infrastructure for microbial resources support for research and development in Europe, where multinational collaboration is currently hampered by the fragmentation of policy, resources and expertise. The creation of MIRRI will be a significant game-changer in terms of elucidating the full value latent in microorganisms and provide a major catalyst to the delivery of a successful bioeconomy.

MIRRI will ensure microorganisms and associated data used in value creation are properly characterised, of a quality that can be relied upon and exploited in such a way that delivers fair returns transparently to the origin. This effort will help underpin European jobs and economic growth with a more efficient bio-industry, help us to better access, exchange and understand knowledge on microbial biodiversity, significantly raise the quality and credibility of microbial science and ensure reproducibility of data and better knowledge creation and diffusion.

Underlying principles

The MIRRI model is based on the following founding principles:

- i. MIRRI will operate on the basis of a non-profit entity, established under the European Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).
- ii. The heart of the MIRRI will be built around an open access infrastructure for handling of and access to expertise, resources and associated data. MIRRI will adhere to the European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures which is in preparation. MIRRI will provide open access for data and materials generated with public funding establishing clear rights on access and use but where it adds value it may develop tools for which it charges. mBRCs will continue to charge for supply of strains. Some services will be market driven and where commercial approaches will be in line with the legal mechanisms establishing MIRRI.
- iii. MIRRI will work to increase capacity to facilitate acquisition of strains to underpin European life sciences and develop a common accession policy to protect the public investment by funders in developing these resources. MIRRI will work with its members to improve their business plans and expand their private funding.
- iv. MIRRI will be open to all European collections that comply with the Rules of Operation and Partner Charter and will help all others meet the requirements.
- v. It will work with Member States to ensure the user communities are part of the governance structure to inform its work and output. The infrastructure's expertise will be focussed and enhanced and mechanisms to facilitate its use and to bring in external expertise developed. MIRRI will thus engender trust with its stakeholders and user communities.
- vi. Virtual platforms of expertise will be organised across the infrastructure to share access and costs.
- vii. Duplication of holdings will be kept to a minimum, consistent with the security and diversity of microbial resources. Thus, as part of the MIRRI Preparatory Phase there is planned rationalisation and consolidation of the offerings of current and future MIRRI partner collections. As a result centres of excellence will be established with national funding.
- viii. Collaborations with other ESFRI consortia, e.g., BBMRI-ERIC, ERINHA, EMBRC, ELIXIR EU-OPENSOURCE, EU-BIOIMAGING, ECRIN, INSTRUCT and ISBE are underway in areas of common interests to avoid duplication and unproductive competition. These will be augmented where it makes sense by international linkages. Collaboration with other European initiatives will also be explored such as ECDC and QBOL. Managing data interoperability and sharing, where appropriate, expertise in curation and analysis of different types of datasets will bring cost efficiencies and new tools. Access to published datasets will be useful for systems biology and access to expertise in a wide range of computational modelling approaches will enable integrating diverse datasets into quantitative and predictive models. Initially MIRRI will provide its strain metadata that will in return add value to partner data. In order to ensure a manageable start for the implementation of MIRRI, minimal requirements for partner collections will have to be formulated. It is the aim of MIRRI to expand and become an inclusive network where collections are able to improve their level of quality.

- ix. MIRRI will work with partners, to develop joint standards for presenting data and providing services that effectively link phenotypic and genomic data for users. This will add significant value to the ESFRI network and the biological resources held.

The Preparatory Phase project is establishing the stakeholder governance mechanisms and an effective Business Plan to deliver and ensure sustainability. It will aim to secure longer term support for subsequent phases, examining suitable business strategy and revenue lines to reach technical, legal and financial maturity. It will provide the tools, concepts and design to enter the implementation and operational phases.

MIRRI's stakeholders

Key to the success of MIRRI is to manage its stakeholders' expectations and to this end a communication and outreach strategy has been prepared (Figure 2). The stakeholders have been identified, their interest and power to influence MIRRI's development and operations assessed and plans for their involvement are underway.

Figure 2. Communication within the MIRRI environment

The MIRRI stakeholders have been assigned to the categories Allies, Supporters, Latents and Bystanders each providing and receiving benefits from MIRRI (Table 2.1 and Figure 3). The **Allies** are the most important stakeholder group, having much power to support the project as well as a high interest in it. As a priority group these stakeholders will be involved in discussions and, in specific cases, brought formally into the decision making processes. A second group the **Supporters** have less power to support the project but a substantial interest in it; these stakeholders are being brought into the project through consultation areas of their interest or actively involving them in various outreach tasks. The **Latents** have the power to support the project, but do not seem to be specifically interested in mBRC activities. Therefore activities to raise their interest will be undertaken potentially leading to their shift to become Allies. Finally the **Bystanders** who have neither much interest in the project nor the power to support it; nevertheless, it may be possible to increase their interest in the project, i.e. shift them to the Supporters or at least prevent their adverse effect through misinformation.

Table 2.1. Stakeholders and their interaction with MIRRI

Stakeholder	Category level of engagement	Goal of interaction
Main National Contributor	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Member State signatory to the MIRRI-ERIC Funder of mBRCs and cluster activities
Other National Contributor	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Member State signatory to the MIRRI-ERIC Funder of mBRCs and cluster activities
Industrial User	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; expert advisory panel for CCU; Governance role
Academic User	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; expert advisory panel for CCU
Civil Service User	Bystanders inform	Collaborator on national policy and regulation
National Collections / mBRCs	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Participants in National Nodes; MIRRI provider, cluster and project collaborator
National and International Patent Offices, Technology Transfer Units	Allies collaborate	IP policy advice; Advisory Board; Business policy advice
Research Funders	Latents consult	Cluster activity funders
Research Establishments / Universities	Allies collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; Collaborators in cluster activities and projects; Advisory; Members expert platforms
Depositors	Allies collaborate	Mind-set change on deposit; collaborators in cluster activities and projects; Uptake of deposit incentive programme
Journal Editors	Supporters involve	Journal policy to encourage deposit of strains
Associations for Training and Education	Supporters involve	Training programmes; Capacity building, Advisory Board
Labour Union, Equal Opportunity Commissioners and Departments	Bystanders inform	Specialist advice;
Legal, Regulatory and Normative Institutions/Authorities	Allies collaborate	Policy development; Expert panel; Advisory Board
Supra-/International Organisations	Allies collaborate	Collaborator; Networking and outreach; Funder; Advisory Board
Media	Bystanders inform	Publicity and outreach
Governing Board (of MIRRI)	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Direction and advice
Advisory Board (of MIRRI)	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Governance, Guidance and expert advice
Biodiversity Associations	Allies collaborate	Conduit for communication with users
Bio-industry Associations	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Conduit for communication with users
EU/ESFRI	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Funder, Advisory Board
EU Infrastructure / Infrastructure projects	Allies, highly relevant collaborate	Collaborators; Advisory Board, network partner
Collection-related Associations and Networks	Allies collaborate	Network partner
Opponents of Biotechnology	Bystanders inform	Ensure they have the right message and information
Government Commission	Allies collaborate	MIRRI lobbyist
Regional Resource Infrastructures (outside Europe)	Supporters involve	Collaborator and network partner

Figure 3: Categorisation of MIRRI stakeholders (1: Main National Contributor, 2: Other National Contributor, 3: Industrial User, 4: Academic User, 5: Civil Service User, 6: National Collections/mBRCs, 7: Patent Offices, Technology Transfer Units, 8: Research Funders, 9: Research Establishments/Universities, 10: Depositors, 11: Journal Publisher, 12: Associations for Training and Education, 13: Labour Union, Equal Opportunity, 14: Legal, Regulatory, Normative Institutions, 15: Supra-/International Organisations, 16: Media, 17: Governing Board (of MIRRI), 18: Advisory Board (of MIRRI), 19: Biodiversity Associations, 20: Bio-industry Associations, 21: EU/ESFRI, 22: EU Infrastructure/Infrastructure projects, 23: Collection-related Associations & Networks, 24: Opponents of biotechnology, 25: Government commission, 26: Regional Resource Infrastructures (outside Europe))

How MIRRI will deliver

This distributed infrastructure facilitates access to a broader range of high quality microorganisms with added value through associated data to help realise their intrinsic value. The products and services will be delivered through the individual mBRC participants but a MIRRI web portal will bring these offers together and show where products and services can be found. Any individual mBRC can be a contact point but their offer will be enhanced by the cross infrastructure holdings and expertise.

MIRRI will offer something new to science and bio-industry by making a paradigm change in the operations of BRCs to ensure they underpin and improve the microbiological sciences, make input on bioeconomies and provide the resources to discover integrated solutions to the grand challenges and to generate knowledge from data. This will be achieved through coordinated acquisition policy that will broaden the range of resources and increase capacity through more efficient use and expansion of facilities with an improved data offer to facilitate the uptake of microbial resources by biotechnologists and accelerate the process chain to discovery of new active molecules.

MIRRI will improve the quality and reproducibility of microbial science (research) by providing validated reference materials and ensuring key strains from the scientific literature and research upon which the science hypotheses hinge are retained for further use. Current training offers will be expanded to make use of state-of-the-art learning tools, give access to

training facilities at various levels (technical, research linked etc.); formal courses and workshops and provide the essential sets of skills to help drive the bioeconomy.

The Data Offer (interoperability to facilitate data mining)

MIRRI will connect its data to other relevant data sets to facilitate the generation of knowledge. Following the principles laid down in the report *Riding the wave* explaining *How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data*¹¹ where the benefits of accelerating the development of a fully functional e-infrastructure for scientific data is described. Interrogating member collections strain data at several levels will enable the identification of potential chemical entities and properties to deliver solutions and indicate where to find them. Utilising phylogenetic hierarchy to extend individual strain data to relatives, or chemistry through host and substrates can lead to a broader range of organisms that have the potential property sought. Additionally, when discoveries are made environments can be identified where more microbial diversity with the property can be found. MIRRI will seek data holding partners and through initiatives of ELIXIR and BioMedBridges will ensure interoperability of its community data to facilitate accelerated discovery and innovation.

There needs to be better interrogation of the hidden value of organisms in the field. Such interrogation should enable exploration, discovery, description and generation of knowledge, not just present the data available. It needs to be:

- specialised – specific collections in a MIRRI matrix have complementary expertise
- targeted - collections become economically and scientifically relevant
- focussed in line with demand and address current and near future needs
- vision-driven - appropriately forward looking and exploratory

The data offering needs to be clearer. Specifically:

- databases need to be coordinated across collections
- integration of data across and between collections
- implementation of minimum data sets

Datasets across and beyond collections need to exist at different levels. These need to be integrated and then data-mined. They need to address:

- ecosystem and habitat
- typical strain properties
- geographical locations
- Genebank – strain number – phenotype – downstream properties linkages
- unambiguous databases of phenotypic properties – e.g. enzymes, metabolites and including chemotaxonomic information
- phylogenetic hierarchy

¹¹ European Union (2010). *Riding the wave. How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data*, Final report of the High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data. A submission to the European Commission. Printed by Osmotica.it. http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/itemlongdetail.cfm?item_id=6204

A short term target for MIRRI is to identify the databases that it needs to develop or link to and ways to integrate them. By applying data standards and ensuring interoperability in the medium term MIRRI users will have access to a data landscape that can be mined for useful properties. MIRRI's data offering will change the game on discovery and exploitation by facilitating the identification of the yet to be discovered value of microbial resources.

Partnership will be key to the success of MIRRI's data strategy and MIRRI must learn lessons from the other ESFRI infrastructures and to work with ELIXIR to ensure data interoperability. The data integration and thus value-added needs to be delivered in three steps:

- Utilise standards for the integration of data within mBRCs according to defined and controlled ontologies; providing a trusted, good and accurate interface. Increase the level of data on the mBRC's own strains from paper information into an electronic format.
- Collaborate with ELIXIR and other ESFRI databases to mine across databases and begin to deliver economically relevant data. This envisages plugging into investment in Big Data and HPC to add information, thus value into the existing large volumes of data in mBRCs. This is a scientific enterprise – with data mining and integration at its heart. The goal is to offer novel data sets and data combinations to very well informed customers who are then able to use such data sets in creating new knowledge and opportunities.
- Turning new data into new knowledge and making that knowledge available through integrated and open knowledge networks. Knowledge presents the hidden value in recognisable terms for investment. It envisages the creation of a knowledge collaboration based on data networking. It is the gold standard of a publicly-funded shared knowledge that integrates MIRRI metadata with for example, EU-OPENSREEN in a way that casts light on G8 aspirations for new antimicrobials. Thus - data path-finding will drive the engine of MIRRI.

Legal certainty on use

MIRRI follows the globally accepted principles of establishment of Biological Resource Centres that not only retain resources and information of high quality but make them available in a legally compliant operational framework. MIRRI will work with resource providers, policy makers and users to provide legal clarity of rights in use and transparency to engender trust. Additionally, MIRRI Partners have established codes of practice, specifically in biosecurity to reduce potential mal intended use. MIRRI will work to provide resources in a safe and compliant way.

The implementation of the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing¹² requires regulatory compliance as well as due diligence in sourcing and seeking legal clarity in use. The Protocol also requires an environment of monitoring and reporting on access and use of genetic resources. Specifically MIRRI will ensure capture of value and benefit to places of origin with respect to their holdings; member mBRCs will follow codes of practice that will facilitate transparency in legality of access and transfer of rights to utilise according to the mutually agreed terms and prior informed consent.

¹² Text of the Nagoya Protocol <http://www.cbd.int/abs/text/default.shtml>

Business models for operations

MIRRI recognises the need of biotechnology industry to keep ahead of its competitors in business and thus the need for confidentiality in sourcing organisms and exchanging information. MIRRI will make available coordinated platforms of resources, tools, data and expertise through controlled and confidential business models. Each individual microbial resource centre will be a point of contact for industry to do business with MIRRI. Thus a company's most appropriate mBRC will not only bring its range of products and services but if needed will have the wealth of 400,000 plus microorganisms and the expertise across the member collections behind it.

Broader access to materials

Having set up its data offer to identify new sources of lead compounds, provided legal certainty of use and appropriate business models MIRRI can reach out to regional and global efforts facilitating access to global resources. Engendered trust, compliant delivery and opportunity to track the use of overseas genetic resources can facilitate access to materials from countries of mega diversity for global science and discovery.

Security of strains for future use and protection of public funding investment

It is clear that scientists do not currently source research strains and deposit their biological materials in public service microbial resource centres. MIRRI wants to change this and will work with journal editors, research funders and scientists to offer incentive for change. It is absolutely essential that if science, particularly microbiology, is to impact on global challenges and the bioeconomy that microbial resource centres need to work together with all stakeholders to achieve this. Improved quality resources with enhanced knowledge from data provided by these centres will make a difference.

Better resources and services to meet stakeholder needs

MIRRI will work with its partners to establish improved management of microbial resources to provide coordinated access to high quality resources. Working with stakeholders to achieve common strategies in acquisition, characterisation and delivery the MIRRI microbial resource centre infrastructure will deliver high quality and protect public investment in the collection and generation of information on microbiological material. MIRRI will deliver efficiency with a common acquisition policy for cultures to increase holdings selectively for more targeted exploitation and to provide a deeper understanding of microbial diversity at the genetic and epigenetic levels and their function in the environment to address global challenges, adding value through characterisation and generating data and delivering capacity to house strains.

Improving transparency, in access and demand/ supply side integration; resources are not currently available in a straight forward and coordinated way – in effect they are “hidden”

- traditional collections are not up to date with current user demands – they are not “new” BRCs as defined by the OECD⁹
- mBRCs need new innovative activities that are well perceived externally

- the properties of unique strains need to be understood and delivered better
- information needs to be available to help people target the right resources for the specific use in mind
- a virtuous handshake needs to be struck between the supply and demand for collections and vice versa. This currently arguably is absent and needs to be at the heart of the MIRRI enterprise
- facilitate links to industry in a timely and appropriate manner
- build a stakeholder community and incorporate this group in the Governance structure
- develop communication targets and channels including a stakeholder forum
- encourage and incentivise the scientist to use mBRCs through improving trust, transparency and mutual collaboration

The MIRRI Preparatory Phase is preparing the strategies and structure to deliver these improvements to the European Research Area. The latter includes appropriate governance, management, statutes and a partner charter.

PARTICIPATION, MANAGEMENT, GOVERNANCE AND CONSTRUCTION

The MIRRI infrastructure itself including its governance structure is being refined during the Preparatory Phase. It will be established under the European Research Infrastructure Consortium¹³ agreement as a distributed model with a Central Coordinating Unit (CCU) as the operational centre. The MIRRI-ERIC statutes set out the main provisions for the governance and management of the MIRRI-ERIC and its services, activities and operations; the detail of the implementation of the statutes is provided in the Rules of Operation. Figure 4 provides the membership components defined in Article 9(1) of Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009. Consequently the membership of MIRRI-ERIC is open to Member States, Associated Countries, Third Countries other than Associated Countries and Intergovernmental Organisations for an initial minimum term of 3 years.

The work programme of MIRRI will be delivered through clusters of experts who will be sourced from both within and outside the RI. Each Member State will establish a National Node to coordinate country activities. Partners beyond Europe will ensure global participation and applicability of outputs. The current iteration of the MIRRI structure is outlined below and is based on models that are already available from other ESFRI consortia that ensure good governance and control.

The MIRRI-ERIC will include some coordinated activities formerly part of the individual mBRC functions. These elements will include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters.

¹³ European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=eric

Structure

European Member States will be invited to sign the MIRRI-ERIC along with EU Associated Countries, Third Countries or Intergovernmental Organizations and thus accept the MIRRI-ERIC Statutes. All can participate either as Full Members or Observers. The legal minimum number of ERIC signatures from Member States to construct the infrastructure is three although the critical mass to provide financial stability may well be 5 members (see D4.1 Financial Plan). The main obligations of Member States are to send a representative to the MIRRI Assembly of Members to provide direction in delivery of appropriate outputs and to provide funding aimed at developing capacity and quality at the national level. The three main elements of the MIRRI structure are the Central Coordinating Unit, the Governing Board and the General Assembly (Figure 5).

Figure 4. MIRRI built using the ERIC structure

Figure 5. MIRRI-ERIC Governance Structure

The MIRRI-ERIC will be steered at a number of levels (see figure 6) the decisions and direction from the General Assembly at the governing level needs to be translated in action and delivered. This will be carried out at the management level under advice of the Advisory Bodies and executed by the CCU.

Figure 6. MIRRI-ERIC Steering levels

Members would contribute to the MIRRI-ERIC budget paying a fee that is yet to be finalised but see estimates made in Deliverable *D4.1 Financial Plan*. Each Member State must

appoint a National Node (NN) and one National Coordinator who is responsible for the country to follow the Assembly of Member's policies. These National Coordinators come together to form the National Coordinator's Forum who appoint a chair to sit on the Governing Board. Up to two experts (one of which should be the National Coordinator) can accompany the Member State representative in the meetings. Each Member State signing the MIRRI-ERIC has one vote, influencing the development of strategies and policies. They also have priority rights from their stakeholders to access the infrastructure services and the possibility to participate in European Union project proposals addressed to RIs. Observing Members in general will be countries in the process of developing appropriate partner facilities or countries or intergovernmental organisations involved in joint projects. They participate in the Assembly of Members but without voting rights, their national stakeholders can apply for access to the Infrastructure services and expertise with priority over non-members to help them establish national nodes and become full participants in the MIRRI-ERIC.

The National Nodes (NNs) will bring together the partners (national mBRCs, experts and service providers) that meet the MIRRI requirements presented in the Partner Charter. The user will have access to strains available in Member NNs as well as directories of other services, thematic clusters, facilities, expertise, data etc. via direct contact with mBRCs, National Nodes or the MIRRI portal. These services will be delivered directly from the providing institutions (mBRCs) belonging to MIRRI, which will maintain the possibility of providing services outside MIRRI. The NNs will coordinate the activities of the partners within the country, to organise funding, to provide or to advise in training issues, to enhance the development of the national mBRCs as well as to expand the national network to improve the MIRRI offer.

Composition of the governing, operational and executive bodies

The decision making body of the MIRRI-ERIC will be the Assembly of Members which is composed of representatives from all Members. As indicated above only Members have voting rights. Observers can contribute by expressing their opinion and can, through their participation in the Assembly of Members, be informed about all decisions taken by this body. It will meet at least once a year; amongst its responsibilities are to appoint the Executive Director, confirm the Executive Officers of the Governing Board, appoint the Advisory Board, decide on strategies for the construction and maintenance of MIRRI, approve the work programme and annual budget of MIRRI-ERIC. The Assembly of Members also approves the Rules of Operation, sets the annual fee for Members and Observers, approves annual reports and accounts of MIRRI-ERIC and approves admission of new Members and Observers. The Assembly of Members elects a President and a Vice President.

The Advisory Board shall advise the Assembly of Members on strategic issues, operation, development, services, etc. The Executive Director will be the responsible to execute all decisions taken by the Assembly helped by the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU).

Governing Board

The Governing Board, appointed by the Assembly of Members, together with the Executive Director form the executive body of the MIRRI-ERIC (Figure 7). The Executive Director is the Chair of the Governing Board. The Assembly of Members appoint the Vice Chair. The Governing Board establishes the Rules of Operation for the MIRRI-ERIC. It is responsible for its operation and implementation of the Work Programme. It follows Assembly of Members' directions and decisions under the guidance of the Advisory Board which may have ethical, scientific, legal and industrial expertise. The activities of MIRRI-ERIC are periodically evaluated by an independent Advisory Board.

Figure 7. Governing Board

Central Coordinating Unit (CCU)

The Executive Director is the legal representative of MIRRI-ERIC, administrator of the MIRRI-ERIC and leader of the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU), recommending the appointment of its staff to the Governing Board. The CCU provides the administration and support services for the general management and administration of the MIRRI-ERIC, is the central point for communication with stakeholders and is responsible for the promotion of the infrastructure. It will be established in one of the EU-Member States signing the MIRRI-ERIC as agreed by the founding Members of the infrastructure.

The CCU will comprise a management office with appropriate staffing. The expertise will include IT Management, a Communication/Customer Relations, Quality Management System expertise and a Secretary. Other skills (Figure 8) will be required to carry out the extended functions of the CCU as it moves into its Implementation Phase including legal and regulatory guidance and support, business development, fund raising, marketing, training, education and technology use and development. The functions of the CCU will include:

- general management of the ERIC, guided by the Governing Board
- prepare policies and strategies for approval by the Governing Board

- handle external user access to the MIRRI Research Infrastructure, preferentially on a collaborative basis with in-house researchers including handling finances related to access
- collaborative project development and management, coordinating the infrastructure with other international initiatives in collaboration with the National Coordinators
- marketing and publicity
- assist shared capacity building, training and education,
- assist in Knowledge and Technology Transfer to SMEs and industry
- managing the technical aspects of mBRCs in collaboration with the National Coordinators
- providing an intergovernmental forum on mBRC issues
- technical issues for membership

The CCU will be responsible for ensuring collaboration and appropriate linkages with stakeholders and in particular related networks and project consortia. At present, many mBRCs are members of international associations such as the European Culture Collections' Organization (ECCO), the World Federation of Culture Collections (WFCC), the World Data Centre for Microorganisms (WDCM), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the Genomic Encyclopedia of Bacteria and Archaea (GEBA), etc. which promote the global integration of microbial biodiversity. Other types of networks such as microbial scientific associations, the European Federation of Biotechnology (EFB) or the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) may help in targeted (academic / bio-industry) MIRRI outreach.

Connections with other closely related ESFRI projects (EU-OPENSREEN, EMBRC or ELIXIR, ISBE, ERINHA, EMTRAIN) have been established and others are being evaluated to determine potential common services. Some have been identified for proposals for Horizon 2020 calls.

Figure 8. MIRRI-ERIC Central Coordinating Unit

A host country will be selected for the CCU. The MIRRI-ERIC will establish a statutory seat and a procedure to aid the process of locating it. There are a number of options to be considered in ensuring these functions can be carried out involving out sourcing, Liaison Officers at each partner for managing practical issues with the CCU but all activities would be under the direction of the MIRRI Executive Director. The Preparatory Phase offers an opportunity for partners to explore with Member States, the willingness and practicalities to host the statutory seat and consequently where the CCU will be located. The process will be one based on open bidding anticipating that the bidder will specify what they offer (staffing, housing, secondary support and sustained financing of the CCU) and some secondary conditions (easy to reach, academic and innovative environment, nearby meeting facilities, etc.). The call will be to all EU Member States and resulting bids will be prioritised by an independent advisor. After proposers have had the opportunity to revise their proposals Member States party to the MIRRI-ERIC at an Assembly of Members will select the favoured proposal.

The operational structure of the MIRRI-ERIC will be a distributed model with a hub and spokes design connecting the CCU to the NNs bringing together the national partners (mBRCs, experts and service providers) that meet the MIRRI requirements. Access to the MIRRI offer will be via a virtual portal, directly via mBRCs or their national nodes (NNs) see Figure 7.

The National Nodes (NNs)

The NN can be at a single national mBRCs or be a National Network represented by a legal entity appointed by the Member State. The mBRCs in the NN will sign up to the MIRRI Partner Charter that will include criteria and specific commitments to data provision and policy adherence. The NN will help network members achieve these criteria and to meet the national needs. NNs will contribute with resources, data, expertise and services to functional transnational expert clusters brought together to solve infrastructure problems and European research community needs and challenges. Each NN will have a coordinator who would accompany the Member State representative at the MIRRI Assembly of Members.

The National Coordinator will act as the main liaison between the MIRRI-ERIC and the National Node. National Coordinators are responsible for their country to follow the Assembly of Members' policies and strategies for the development and exploitation of the research infrastructure. A National Coordinators' Forum of all National Coordinators will be established to ensure the implementation of the strategies laid out by the Assembly of Members. The forum has to maintain coherence and consistency across the distributed infrastructure and collaboration between National Nodes.

Figure 9. Generation of annual MIRRI Working Plan

Clusters of expertise

The clusters of expertise will be the main functional unit. The work programme for MIRRI will be designed and agreed by the Assembly of Members as presented in figure 9. They can be brought together on an *ad-hoc* basis responding to concrete demands and can be of short or long-term duration. There are several that constitute the pillars of MIRRI and, as such, will be assembled from the beginning. These may include:

- Legal issues concerning the handling, delivery and use of microbial resources. This cluster will help both users and providers to comply with biosafety, biosecurity, IPR and ABS regulations
- Taxonomic platforms of experts and technologies that can support both mBRCs and the user community in identification, authentication and selection of strains.
- Application-driven, providing an opportunity for experts to be brought together for example to provide microbial solutions in food security or healthcare or help a user address a specific need, a technological problem or source the most appropriate organisms for a specific property.
- Further develop preservation technology to broaden the range of organisms stored improving reliability and reproducibility.
- Quality management.
- Data management and delivery.
- New technologies application and coordination of use.

Transnational clusters to address issues such as coverage of quarantine reference materials, perform geno- and phenotyping of resources or provide expertise at different levels (particular taxa or environment, methods, etc.) are foreseen. Harnessing existing projects and networks can be the basis to harmonize or develop these kinds of clusters.

Partner Charter

Membership in MIRRI-ERIC, at both Member (the Member States etc.) and Partner level (NNs and mBRCs), does not influence any activity outside the MIRRI-ERIC statutes. The Partner Charter defines criteria that are to be met by the partners and criteria for resource and service providers (mBRCs) as follows:

- i. Must demonstrate satisfactorily to the Assembly of Members the implementation of a **quality management system (QMS)** following the principles of the **OECD Best Practice Guidelines for mBRCs** (criteria will be set and assessed via the QMS cluster; partners will be accepted via the Assembly of Members)
- ii. Commit themselves to be, at any time, **transparent** to customers. Partners will clearly indicate which services and collection components are part of the MIRRI consortium, and as such are guaranteed by MIRRI quality standards.
- iii. Guarantee **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)** access to microbial resources they bring to MIRRI by complying with the general requirements of MIRRI.
- iv. Commit themselves to implement the **MIRRI policy** in compliance with the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)**.
- v. Commit themselves to implement **biorisk assessment and biosecurity** measures as described in the ERIC statutes.
- vi. Agree to design (through the Heads of Collections forum), contribute to and implement a **common accession policy** that is based on broadening the range of strains available, reducing duplication and increasing capacity.
- vii. Commit themselves to develop a **sustainability strategy** to ensure that their MIRRI holdings and services remain available for the consortium.
- viii. Commit themselves to **provision of data and information** to meet MIRRI's data management and delivery need.
- ix. Commit themselves to **participation in applicable cluster activities** and implement resulting harmonised practices, strategies and policies.
- x. Actively seek **bio-industry interaction** and responding to advice.
- xi. Exceptions regarding the membership criteria can be established but have to follow transparent decision-making procedures and be approved by the Assembly of Members.

A mechanism will be defined for achieving membership status (see figure 10). Members will need to comply with the partner charter and expected to reach good levels of compliance management.

Figure 10. Assignment Process for MIRRI Partners

MIRRI-ERIC Advisory Bodies and Advisory Board

Figure 11. MIRRI-ERIC Advisory Bodies and Advisory Board

A sound operational framework for MIRRI is crucial for compliance with community best practices in business operation, the legal environment, access to resources delivery and

communication to its stakeholders. A strong panel of advisory bodies is needed to keep pace with the ever changing environment and as checkpoints for performance (see figure 11).

These bodies will not only impact on the governance of the MIRRI-ERIC but their advice will be valuable for the national nodes and partner mBRCs. The relationship between the nodes and the CCU will be critical. The National nodes will coordinate outputs at the national level with the major services of biological resources and data directly accessed at the mBRC (figure 12).

The Governance structure will be tested over the final year of the preparatory phase of MIRRI. Its impact on the business planning and especially the costs of the operation will be taken into account for the implementation phase. Processes for financial control are being developed, with the current estimations of costs and the sources of revenue, these are outlined in the next section, the financial plan.

Figure 12. Partners and Offers in MIRRI-ERIC National Node

Summary

The MIRRI Statutes present the different bodies of the governance structure, defining their responsibilities and the interdependencies between them as well as the decision-making process of the research infrastructure. MIRRI will implement a Work Program as adopted by the Assembly of Members (Article 3) MIRRI-ERIC Member States will be bound by the statutes and the National Nodes and constituent mBRCs by the Rules of Operation and Partner Charter content. The Assembly of Members will be the decision-making body of MIRRI-ERIC and will decide on strategies for the construction, maintenance and development of MIRRI; approve the work program and annual budget of MIRRI-ERIC; approve the Rules of Operation and any amendments to the Rules of Operation; approve annual reports on work achieved. The Executive Director through the Central Coordinating

Unit will implement the decisions and programs adopted by the Assembly of Members and submit the annual activity report. The Governing Board will be responsible for the operation of MIRRI-ERIC following the Assembly of Members directions and decisions, as well as the counsel from the Advisory Bodies. The National Coordinators Forum consisting of all National/Organisational Coordinators will implement the directions and decisions taken by the Assembly of Members, as well as the counsel from the Advisory Board, at the level of the Members and their national institutions. The work programme will address the coordinated aspects managed by the MIRRI-ERIC. The National Nodes and national mBRCs retain their own legal entity but the control of some elements of their activities is transferred to the MIRRI-ERIC according to the MIRRI-ERIC charter.

FINANCIAL IMPLICATIONS

The MIRRI Financial Plan has been presented separately as *Deliverable 4.1 Financial plan* and provides key information for the Business Plan and ultimately for the success of MIRRI. The MIRRI approach assumes a not-for-profit entity that is sustained by a mixed funding model implying long term core support by participating Member States and income generation by the MIRRI Partners, some through centrally coordinated activities. The Financial Plan describes a balance being struck between core support and income generation. There are two distinct cost centres, the MIRRI-ERIC implemented by the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU) and the second around National Nodes (NNs) and their networked mBRCs. The costs and revenues are summarised in Table 4.1 and include the personnel associated with the CCU, its operational costs and accommodation and consumable costs for the office, data storage, maintenance and use, governance, communication, cluster operation and access. These costs total almost €6.2 million. Income from sources including Member State contributions to the MIRRI-ERIC, partner mBRC fees, third party grants, income from access to facilities, data and expertise and CCU host country contributions is anticipated at around €6.9 million providing a small surplus for investment. The Member State contributions are calculated on the basis of country GDP and presented in the Financial Plan. At this Preparatory Phase, the expected expenditures of the CCU are conceived as the establishment and operation of the MIRRI core services, such as provision of a secretariat for governance and oversight functions, provision and operation of central data services and general support for the operation of the network aspects of the MIRRI consortium. The tasks are limited to coordinating access to data and facilities with a low level of development thus costs have been minimised.

CCU operations

Staff are allocated to tasks to direct the CCU outputs and coordinate MIRRI core activities; the costs can be split into three areas:

- 1) CCU Infrastructure costs (covered by the host country) which include accommodation, running costs, communication and outreach, project and stakeholder meetings
- 2) CCU operations including advisory roles and bodies, travel and accommodation, IT node and expert platforms
- 3) CCU personnel

Currently these costs are estimated at €6.2 million over the first 5 years for operating the MIRRI-ERIC with most costs being attributed to the key elements of data delivery to facilitate uptake of the microbial resources, giving access to expert platforms and user access to

research facilities and resources. It is also possible that some of the costs would be covered by the CCU Host Member State.

MIRRI operates a distributed “hub and spoke” mechanism where the CCU coordinates activities through the National Nodes (NNs) and the delivery of resources, expertise and most services is through the national mBRCs. The node-specific expenditure is dependent upon a number of factors including the total number of mBRCs participating, the degree of development and maturation of the node, the extent to which mBRCs have devolved some of their activities to a central unit and local costs. The funding of the mBRCs and the NNs is a national obligation outside the costings for the MIRRI-ERIC and to a great extent depends on the level of involvement of national funders. This varies from country to country but is considered an essential part of mBRC business model as perceived by the OECD⁹.

Costs at the mBRC level

These costs include those incurred by mBRCs to meet the Partner Charter and those associated with the demands upon them from the MIRRI-ERIC. The MIRRI Partner Charter requires the implementation of best practices, technology development and strengthening of mBRC expertise. Costs at the level of the MIRRI-ERIC concern the collection expansion to increase capacity for strains allocated via the common accession policy; participation in expert platforms and the delivery of transnational access to facilities and resources. These costs do not reflect mBRC full costs only those additional costs of participating in the MIRRI-ERIC. Cost efficiencies, opportunities to participate in funded activities and support in development give partner mBRCs incentive and advantage to join MIRRI.

Cost estimates are averaged across country boundaries and do not take into account the different organisms and the level of complication of handling some of them and the extent to which some collections characterise strains. Nevertheless, there is solid methodology to these estimates. In order to upgrade mBRCs to reach the operational requirement level, for example implementing OECD best practice and expanding capacity to authenticate and store additional holdings, they will need, to varying degrees, depending on their current level of development, to establish a quality management system. Work in the GBRCN¹⁴ and EMbaRC projects demonstrated that these costs vary depending on the size of the operation and type of quality management system that is implemented. There are additional recurrent (staff) costs to maintain the quality system. The National Nodes will also have one-off constructional and development costs and recurring operational costs. Generally it is anticipated that costs will tail off and that long term activities need to be supported by the individual mBRC budgets supported by improved revenue lines and institutional and government funding where appropriate. In large part, the measure of the success of MIRRI will be the breadth and depth of these activities and the extent to which revenue generation for them can be channelled to augment further developments.

MIRRI aims to support mBRCs to become sustainable and outlines here some of the many financial models currently in operation across the microbial resource collections world. MIRRI will assist its participant collections to introduce the most appropriate business plans and ensure best value for money. It is evident that both the mBRCs and the MIRRI infrastructure

¹⁴ Fritze, D., Martin, D. & Smith, D. (2012). Final report on the GBRCN Demonstration Project. Germany: GBRCN Secretariat. ISBN 978-3-00-038121-8.

require support funding and they must be balanced funding one at the expense of the other would not work.

Table 4.1 Investments and costs for the MIRRI-ERIC Central Coordinating Unit and its operations

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	TOTAL
CCU infrastructure investments						
Membership fees	949,984.87 €	922,668.70 €	1,034,756.81 €	1,037,468.28 €	1,037,468.28 €	4,982,346.94 €
Observer fees	76,073.10 €	103,389.27 €	96,518.04 €	42,276.19 €	49,776.19 €	368,032.79 €
Partner fees mBRCs	25,000.00 €	30,000.00 €	35,000.00 €	45,000.00 €	60,000.00 €	195,000.00 €
Partner fees other partners	5,000.00 €	7,000.00 €	9,000.00 €	12,000.00 €	15,000.00 €	48,000.00 €
Third grants	24,000.00 €	49,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	280,000.00 €
Host country input	171,000.00 €	182,925.00 €	195,717.38 €	209,441.37 €	224,493.83 €	983,577.58 €
Income data access and expert clusters	- €	2,000.00 €	5,500.00 €	9,000.00 €	16,000.00 €	32,500.00 €
TOTAL Income	1,251,057.97 €	1,296,982.97 €	1,445,492.22 €	1,424,185.84 €	1,471,738.30 €	6,856,957.30 €
CCU infrastructure costs - host country						
Accommodation	20,000.00 €	20,600.00 €	21,218.00 €	21,854.54 €	22,837.99 €	106,510.53 €
Running costs	11,000.00 €	11,825.00 €	12,711.88 €	13,665.27 €	14,690.16 €	63,892.30 €
Communication and Outreach	40,000.00 €	43,000.00 €	46,225.00 €	49,691.88 €	53,418.77 €	232,335.64 €
Annual meeting, stakeholder meeting	100,000.00 €	107,500.00 €	115,562.50 €	124,229.69 €	133,546.91 €	580,839.10 €
CCU infrastructure costs						
Advice	30,000.00 €	32,250.00 €	34,668.75 €	37,268.91 €	40,064.07 €	174,251.73 €
Advisory Board	20,000.00 €	21,500.00 €	23,112.50 €	24,845.94 €	26,709.38 €	116,167.82 €
Travel and accommodation	140,000.00 €	150,500.00 €	161,787.50 €	173,921.56 €	186,965.68 €	813,174.74 €
IT node	50,000.00 €	53,750.00 €	57,781.25 €	62,114.84 €	66,773.46 €	290,419.55 €
Expert platforms	100,000.00 €	107,500.00 €	115,562.50 €	124,229.69 €	133,546.91 €	580,839.10 €
CCU costs for personnel						
Director	152,400.00 €	156,972.00 €	161,681.16 €	166,531.59 €	171,527.54 €	809,112.30 €
Secretary	63,500.00 €	65,405.00 €	67,367.15 €	69,388.16 €	71,469.81 €	337,130.12 €
IT Manager	127,000.00 €	130,810.00 €	134,734.30 €	138,776.33 €	142,939.62 €	674,260.25 €
Communication, public relation	82,550.00 €	85,026.50 €	87,577.30 €	90,204.61 €	92,910.75 €	438,269.16 €
Compliance Officer – legal, QMS	127,000.00 €	130,810.00 €	134,734.30 €	138,776.33 €	142,939.62 €	674,260.25 €
Business development, grants	- €	- €	- €	- €	127,000.00 €	127,000.00 €
Technology Transfer Officer	- €	- €	- €	- €	82,550.00 €	82,550.00 €
Training and education	- €	- €	- €	- €	76,200.00 €	76,200.00 €
TOTAL CCU expenses	1,063,450.00 €	1,117,448.50 €	1,174,724.08 €	1,235,499.34 €	1,586,090.68 €	6,177,212.60 €
Over/underfunding	187,607.97 €	179,534.47 €	270,768.14 €	188,686.50 €	-114,352.38 €	712,244.70 €
Account balance /year	- €	187,607.97 €	367,142.44 €	637,910.58 €	826,597.08 €	2,019,258.07 €

Income Generation

Financial contributions are anticipated from the Members to fund the MIRRI-ERIC. The level of financial contributions of the Members (including a minimum annual monetary contribution) is to be determined by the Assembly of Members. The contribution is calculated based on GDP per capita, and a fixed rate applicable to all; details are provided in *Deliverable 4.1 The Financial Plan*. Additionally, funding will be sought from funded projects or revenue generation from services provided by the central coordinating node. This may include licensing of any applicable intellectual property rights (IPRs). As such income grows the costs to Member States will reduce. Any further revenue generated through MIRRI-ERIC via centrally coordinated activities will be retained by MIRRI and spent on such matters as are decided by the Assembly of Members thus reducing costs further to Member States. Third party grants would rise over the years to around 30% of income with additional contributions coming from the CCU's Host Member State, access fees and membership fees. Following the initial investments to upgrade national mBRCs to function as National Nodes governmental costs would focus on support of the day-to-day operations of nodes and participating mBRCs. However, change in direction of some of the spend of this funding would be anticipated; currently there is little available for improvement of services and keeping pace with technology it is envisaged that due to increased efficiencies and shared activity cost across the research infrastructure funds would be available for introduction of new technologies and additional expertise needed to develop new and innovative services and products. Additional targeted public expenditures may also be appropriate to ensure mBRCs make optimal contributions to the Member State-level bioeconomy.

Table 4.2 shows in percentage terms how MIRRI sees the necessary revenue being generated. It can be seen that it is anticipated that investment by Member States in financing the MIRRI-ERIC will reduce from 75% in year one to 50% cover of costs in year 5.

Table 4.2 MIRRI-ERIC Funding investment model showing percentage split between the different sources

Funding source	Funding level (percentage of total cost)				
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5**
Member States (6 signatories)	75	63	58	55	50
Third Party Grants	12.5	25	35	35	35
Coordinating hub host country	12.5	10	2	2	2
Bioindustry	0	1	3	4.5	8
mBRC membership fees	0	1	2	3.5	5
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Funding will be more or stable in years 6-10

WHAT NEEDS TO HAPPEN NOW

The Preparatory Phase will establish the statutes and documentation necessary for the establishment of the MIRRI-ERIC. Currently it is difficult to estimate the exact number of Member States that will participate. The commitment to MIRRI has mainly been expressed through the mBRCs themselves but many have some national government support in this. In placing MIRRI on the ESFRI road map state representatives expressed their full support but with no commitment to fund. It is a key priority to engage with States and secure financial commitment for its future development and operation. To get this commitment in the first instance countries are being invited to sign up to the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Third Iteration Business Plan presenting key information to help them make that commitment. To date France, Poland, Spain and Greece have signed a MoU without financial commitment at this stage and Belgium and Germany are looking at the finances and mechanisms for operating the CCU. Other Preparation Phase partner countries are being asked to engage these countries include Czech Republic, Portugal, Russia, Italy, The Netherlands, Sweden and the UK. The MIRRI-ERIC critical mass is considered 5 Member States to be financially viable. It will take time to reach this level of participation and it is anticipated that there will be an interim phase between the Preparatory Phase ending and the implementation of MIRRI. Currently drafts of the four documents needed to implement the MIRRI-ERIC are underway and final versions of these will be needed in the short-term.

The Interim Phase

Interim measures will need to be put in place prior to the signing of the MIRRI-ERIC. To date, it is envisaged that interested Member States will sign a MoU and subsequently be invited to join an Interim Governing Board. The National Nodes would keep their own legal status within states. Interested Member States will be invited to send one technical and one administrative delegate each to the Interim Board.

It is envisaged that a Scientific Advisory Board would be established by the Interim Board – which subsequently could be validated by the Full Board. The duties of the Scientific Advisory Board are yet to be fully determined but would include support on strategy, work programme design (see figure 9) and operational issues; they would review proposals for further development of the infrastructure and proposals for new members. The Scientific Advisory Board would ensure user benefits are delivered from the improved quality management of mBRCs delivering a consistent level of service and better access to authentic and reproducible materials in a transparent and traceable way.

It is clear that there will be a gap in funding between the Preparatory Phase and the implementation of MIRRI (signing of the MIRRI-ERIC). The key partners have demonstrated in the past their commitment to such purposes, for example the continuation of the CABRI activities from project closure to date. The Steering Committee have some institutional support to continue work during this period to keep the process on track. An interim Governing Board will be organised to start the negotiation of the MIRRI-ERIC.

The governance structure during the Operational Phase will be an extension of that created in the Implementation Phase adapting as more participants join to ensure representation but keeping a manageable number of decision makers. MIRRI is quite lucky as there are

numerous RIs that go before it that it can benefit from the experience of; MIRRI will work with these RIs and the stakeholders to ensure a sound mechanism.

MIRRI must accelerate its development process. Annexe I provides a list of the Preparatory Phase work packages (WP) that build the structure and define its outputs. It is clear that the strategies and infrastructure design form WP 2 'Design of the Microbial Resource Research distributed Infrastructure' and WP 3 'Define governance structure, legal status and operational practice' are key to delivering the final version of this Business Plan and its financial implications. All work packages are designed to improve the intrinsic strength of MIRRI mBRCs.

Strategy for engagement of national funders

Partners are requested to continue discussions with the most appropriate government contacts using the MIRRI Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and the third iteration of the Business Plan and report back. Partners should select the appropriate representatives from the lists of ESFRI delegates and country Research Infrastructure Committee representatives. Alternatively, Partners may already have direct contact with the relevant government department and this contact should be the starting point for engagement. MIRRI partners will report back on outcomes, WP4 task leaders and the Steering Committee will collate the feedback and share lessons learned with partners. MIRRI preparatory phase partners should engage their ministries and main funders in reviewing the MIRRI-ERIC documentation and design to ensure they develop in the right way.

Anticipated outcomes and impact:

Placement of MIRRI on national roadmaps: national representative signature to the MoU will signal national commitment which is the first step to an ERIC.

Steps in establishing MIRRI

- engage users, mBRCs, governments and funders with Business Plan, draft Statutes, Partner Charter and Rules of Operation
- signature on MoU or letter in support of the principles of MIRRI
- set up interim Governing Board with participation of Member States expressing interest
- expand MIRRI's Advisory Board to include representation of the research and industrial communities being served by MIRRI
- establish Interim Governing Board (currently the EC Preparatory Phase contracted Coordinator supported by the Steering Committee)
- utilise the MIRRI Preparatory Phase secretariat to establish the central hub; a process for selection of future central hub will be designed and implemented
- test the managerial conduits to direct the secretariat, National Nodes and mBRC participants in delivering MIRRI outputs and finalise governance structure
- establish/select an interim legal entity to allow MIRRI to operate in the run-up to enough ERIC signatures to formally create MIRRI as an independent body.
- seek commitments to funding
- establish MIRRI when a critical mass of 5 nations sign up to the MoU and at least 10 mBRCs have reached the BRC standard for participation

Timeframe for delivery of MIRRI

activity	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
engage users					
signature on MoU or letter of support					
set up interim Governing Board					
expand MIRRI's Advisory Board					
establish the CCU					
test the managerial conduits					
finalise Governance structure					
establish interim legal entity					
seek commitments to funding					
Interim Phase					
establish the MIRRI-ERIC					
establish MIRRI: Operational Phase					

In summary: Why should governments support MIRRI?

Delivery of high quality microbial resources with facilities to data mine associated data sets will facilitate research and accelerate the discovery of new products and stimulate innovative microbial solutions to the Grand Challenges. MIRRI will facilitate this by ensuring interoperability between microbial strain data and other relevant data sets such as DNA and protein sequences, ecological data, metabolites, geographical data and phylogenetic relationships. MIRRI will deliver a coordinated accession policy to broaden coverage of resources, increase capacity to store and deliver more characterised microorganisms to researchers.

The MIRRI-ERIC will include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters. mBRC participation in the MIRRI National Nodes will be governed by commitments made in the Partner Charter which will include delivery of high quality data to agreed standards, participation in capacity building programmes and a commitment to deliver the MIRRI communication and outreach strategy to stakeholders particularly to bio-industry.

This will enhance knowledge underpinning research and education, deliver efficiency and cost effectiveness in the management of microbial resources and protect the investment in publicly funded research. The long-term access to the biological materials on which the science is based will enable confirmation of results and further work facilitating high quality research and good science. The Research Infrastructure will support academic and industrial research with high quality services and material. The societal impact will be to improve the economy and create employment through the biotechnological discoveries in healthcare, food security and livelihoods that MIRRI will underpin.

Annexe I: Work Packages

The design of the MIRRI infrastructure and its work programmes and activities is being taken forward through a series of interrelated work packages (WP).

- WP 1 MIRRI preparatory phase project management
- WP 2 Design of the Microbial Resource Research distributed Infrastructure
- WP 3 Define governance structure, legal status and operational practice
- WP 4 Financial plan
- WP 5 Communication, dissemination and outreach
- WP 6 Development of services, outputs and foster interdisciplinary work programs
- WP 7 Capacity building, education and training
- WP 8 Data resources management
- WP 9 Legal operational framework for access to Microbial Resources
- WP 10 Delivering innovation

The work packages address the key issues that have arisen in the design and development of other RIs.

It is imperative that all stakeholders are involved from an early stage, particularly the potential funders. Work package 5 identifies all the relevant stakeholders, provides a strategy for their engagement and coordinates these tasks across work packages assigning priorities, action plans and timelines. Partners will use the output of Work package 4, the business plan and engagement strategy to introduce MIRRI on their national roadmaps and in Operational Programmes for Structural Funds.

A key and early activity is the design of the legal and governance structure (Work package 3) with the supporting sustainable financial plan in order to reduce the lead time in solving legal and governance issues. Collaboration and outreach, the subject of Work package 5, as well as Work package 6, aim to develop the capacity for MIRRI to operate Transnational Access as a potential instrument to ensure the best use of available project funds dependent on the specific situation of the RI and its services.

MIRRI is aware of the need in its Preparatory Phase to develop measures to reduce legal and other barriers to cross border access to the resources of the distributed RI (Work package 9).

Work package 7 addresses capacity building, education and training both within the infrastructure to ensure an increasing set of expertise to deliver its products and services but to the outside also, in transnational access for users. The data resources management of MIRRI will be addressed by work package 8 ensuring user input in design of the information system to ensure user needs are properly addressed. An appropriate legal operational framework for access to microbial resources is essential and this must be compatible outside Europe, work package 9 will address key issues such as Access and Benefit Sharing through implementation of the Nagoya Protocol as well as biosecurity issues. All through the preparatory phase delivering innovative approaches will be at the forefront and work package 10 examines appropriate mechanisms for taking key ideas forward for delivery in the implementation and operational phases.

Annex II: MIRRI Advisory Board

The chair of the Advisory Board is Professor Iain Gillespie, University of Edinburgh and he will take up the role of Director of Science, National Environmental Research Council, UK. Previously he was Head of the Science and Technology Policy Division of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), prior to that head of the OECD's Biotechnology Division (2001-2011) and he led the OECD BRC initiative and helped to design the OECD approach to the Bioeconomy. He is ably supported by Professor Indriķis Muiznieks, Professor of Microbiology and Immunology at the University of Latvia a full Member of the Latvian Academy of Sciences, Head of the Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology and Vice-rector for Research, Latvia; Dame Janet Thornton, Director of the European Bioinformatics Institute on the Wellcome, Trust Genome Campus at Hinxton, UK; Professor Dr. Maria Lodovica Gullino, University of Torino, Professor in Biological and integrated Plant Disease Management, University of Torino; Director of the Centre of Competence AGROINNOVA and Vice-Rector for International Affairs and President of the International Society for Plant Pathology (ISPP), Italy; and Daniel Ramon, Biopolis SL as Chief Scientific Officer, previously Professor at the Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology of the National Spanish Research Council, and prior to that Professor of Food Technology at the University of Valencia, Spain.

Annex III: Glossary and Abbreviations

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Member: EU-Member States, associated countries, third countries or intergovernmental organizations that sign the MIRRI-ERIC as members and make a full contribution to the MIRRI budget.

Observer: EU-Member States, associated countries, third countries or intergovernmental organizations that are in the process of developing appropriate partner facilities or that want to be involved in joint projects with specific scope and time perspective. They sign the MIRRI-ERIC as observers and make a partial contribution to the MIRRI budget.

Partner: mBRC or institution providing resources or services or participating in joint projects in the frame of MIRRI.

National Node: Operational body present in each MIRRI Member State that coordinates the activities of the partners within the country, organises funding, provides or advises in training issues, enhances the development of the national mBRCs as well as expands the national network to improve the offer.

ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Associated Countries
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
BRC	Biological Resource Centre
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
DSMZ	Leibniz Institut DSMZ - Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen / Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganism and Cell Cultures
ECDC	European Centre of Disease and Prevention Control
ECCO	European Culture Collections´ Organisation
ELIXIR	European Life Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
EMbaRC	European Consortium of Microbial Resource Centres
EmBRC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERINHA	European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU-OPENSREEN	European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology
EVA	European Virus Archive
GBRCN	Global Biological Resource Centre Network
INSTRUCT	Integrated Structural Biology Infrastructure for Europe
K	1.000
MIRRI	Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
mBRC	Microbial domain Biological Resource Centre
MS	Member States
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
Q-Bol	Quarantine Barcode of Life
QMS	Quality Management System
RI	Research Infrastructure
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
WFCC	World Federation for Culture Collections
WP	Work Package
y	year